

Different Methods of Arabic Language Teaching and A Proposed Approach to Understanding the Quran for General Educated People of Bangladesh

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Abstract

The importance and significance of learning the language of the Qur'an is clear to us for the right guidance of the entire human being. As a part of that, the study is divided into several parts with the aim of teaching the language of the Quran more easily to the general educated population of Bangladesh. First of all, the popular methods of teaching Arabic language are properly discussed. Based on these methods, some of the most useful courses have been analyzed in detail, mentioning the positive and negative aspects of various courses of Arabic language for understanding the Quran going on worldwide. And finally based on the above analysis some important recommendations are made by us; If a course is designed by implementing the recommendations, it will be an opportunity for the general educated population of Bangladesh to master the language of the Quran more easily.

Key Words: Language teaching methods, Arabic Language, Quranic Arabic Language, General Educated people.

01. Introduction:

Allah SWT revealed the Holy Qur'an to mankind with the aim of salvation the world humanity. The language of Quran is Arabic. Allah SWT says, "I have revealed this Quran in clear Arabic. (Al-Quran, 26:195)" Allah SWT says elsewhere, "I have simplified this Qur'an in the Arabic language. (Al-Quran, ١٩: ٩٧) " Therefore, there is no alternative to learn the language of Quran and Arabic language for the salvation of the world humanity. Keeping this requirement in mind, various courses and curricula have been developed over the ages to understand the language of the Quran. There are also differences in courses and curriculum in the light of caste, gender, age, profession differences. The research will focus on and proposed what the most perfect method can be for the general educated people of Bangladesh and we have given some specific recommendations by analyzing which are the most perfect courses among the ongoing courses; In the light of which, if a course is arranged, the general educated Quranic students of Bangladesh will be able to understand the language of the Quran more easily.

02. Methodology:

descriptive and analytical methods are followed in this study. Various methods of teaching Arabic language are described and their positive and negative aspects are analyzed. Based on this analysis, a suitable and proper course of Quranic Arabic language is proposed in the light of the latest methods of language teaching.

03. Objective of this Study:

- A. Presenting a proposal for the formulation of a course most suitable for the general educated population of Bangladesh;
- b. To present the language of the Quran more easily to the Bengali speaking people;
- c. Above all, to make the Quran easy to understand for the people of all walks of people in Bangladesh.

04. Different methods of Arabic language teaching

The methods of teaching other languages in different contexts have been used for ages, teaching Arabic has not been an exception. Because all the languages of the world have a similarity. Therefore, in teaching Arabic language, the popular methods of teaching and learning other languages have been followed also. These are mentioned bellow in details.

A. Grammar and Translation Method of Arabic Language Teaching

Process of grammar and translation Method:

Analysis of Language (Sounds - Letters - Words – Sentences)

Mastery and arrangement of rules (Word formation and transformation - Different types of phrases .

Translation of various sentences and passages from target language to mother tongue and from mother tongue to target language.

Such grammar analysis and translation based language teaching methods are known as 'Grammar and Translation Method'. Dr. Rushdie Ahmad Tu'aima says:

يقصد بالمنهج النحوي تقديم المحتوى اللغوي في شكل محاور عامة تدور حول موضوعات القواعد استنادا إلى منطقتين مؤدى. أولهما: أن اللغة نظام، والنظام يشتمل على مجموعة من القواعد التي لو تعلمها الفرد أصبح قادرا على استخدام اللغة؛ ومؤدى المنطق الثاني، هو أن لكل معنى تركيبا لغويا يناسبه، وعلينا أن نحصر التراكيب المختلفة التي تنقل معاني معينة تسير للإنسان الاتصال باللغة.

Grammatical system refers to the presentation of language content in a general form; Which basically revolves around the rules of grammar based on two arguments. One. language is a constitution of how many rules, if a person learns it, he is able to use that language; Two. For each meaning there is a corresponding linguistic corollary. We should master various tricks; which carry specific meanings and make it possible for humans to communicate through language. (طعيمة, ١٩٨٩). Dr. Rushdi Ahmad said in this context:

إن هدف تدريس النحو ليس تحفيظ الطالب مجموعة من القواعد المجردة أو التراكيب المنفردة، وإنما مساعدة على فهم التعبير الجيد وتذوقه، وتدريبه على أن ينتجه صحيحا بعد ذلك. وما فائدة النحو إذا لم يساعد الطالب على قراءة نص يفهمه أو التعبير عن شيء فيجيد التعبير عنه؟

Grammar lessons are not about memorizing a set of grammar rules or isolated structures (rules of sentence structure) for learners (without vast examples and exercises). Rather, its purpose is to assist the student in using them to express themselves beautifully, to enjoy their beauty, and to practice them in order to use them productively later on. If a student reads a text but he does not understand the meaning, nor can express his thoughts beautifully and elegantly on any subject - then what is the need or benefit of grammar lessons? (طعيمة, ١٩٨٩)

In modern times, a language is not considered to be known unless it has mastered the four basic skills (listening, speaking, reading and writing). But the grammar-translation method focuses only on reading and writing. Two important skills—listening and speaking—are largely neglected. In this context, Dr. Hammadah said:

التركيز على مهارتي القراءة و الكتابة بل والاقتصار عليهما وإهمال السماع والنطق و هما الأساس في تعليم أي لغة حتى اللغة القومية. فاللغة هي ما تسمعه ونطقه، أما ما نقرأه ونكتبه فما هو إلا رموز متفق عليه، ويؤدي هذا الإهمال الكامل لمهارتي السماع والنطق إلى عجز الدارس عن فهم ما يوجه إليه من حديث وبالتالي عجزه عن المشاركة فيه.

This approach revolves around, and even then is limited to, reading and writing skills. As a result listening and speaking abilities are completely ignored. But these two skills are fundamental or basic skills in learning any language - even mother tongue. Because what we hear and speak is language. And what we read and write from the book, it is nothing but a number of symbols accepted by consensus. Neglect and total neglect of the two basic skills of listening and speaking, leads the student to be unable to understand the oral speech presented to him and to participate in the conversation.(إبراهيم, n.d.)

B. Direct Method of Arabic Language Teaching

Process of Direct Method:

This method relies on teaching the new language directly without taking the intermediary of another language. When the teacher wants to teach some words, such as - chair, door, window etc.; Then his job will be to identify and specify these things in front of the students in the classroom, such as this, that, etc. And when he wants to teach some actions like walking, eating, writing: then he will imitate and say those actions. Thus, all the subjects and objects found in the classroom and close at hand, this method directly expresses them in the desired language. And what is not available in the classroom, the teacher teaches them by showing pictures and examples in the book. Then the practice and practice of using language directly in the classroom is applied in a real and practical environment outside the classroom. For that, what is seen in the eyes, what comes to the mind and what is expressed in the mouth - everything is directly expressed in the intended language.

In this method the student tries to speak directly in the target language. As a result speech is given great importance. Reading and writing are less important in it. Dr. Abdur Rahman Al-Fawzan said:

الاهتمام بمهارة الكلام، بدلا من مهارتي القراءة والكتابة

This method gives importance to speaking skills instead of reading and writing skill. (الفوزان، (٢٠١١)

Dr. Muhammad Ali Al-Khuli said:

تعطي الطريق المباشرة الأولوية لمهارة الكلام بدلا من مهارة القراءة والكتابة والترجمة، على أساس أن اللغة هي الكلام بشكل أساسي

In addition to reading and writing, translation in this manner (from native language to target language, from target language to native language) is strictly prohibited. (الخولي، ١٩٨٦).

Dr. Ali Al-Khuli said:

تتجنب هذه الطريقة استخدام الترجمة في تعليم اللغة الأجنبية، وتعتبرها عديمة ، بل شديدة الضرر على تعليم اللغة المنشودة وتعلمها

In the field of foreign language education, this method is far from translation practice and considers it to be ineffective. Rather, it considers the translation as highly detrimental to learning and teaching the desired language. (الخولي، ١٩٨٦) Dr. Rushdie says:

الترجمة من وإلى العربية أمر ترفضه، هذه الطريقة، فلا ينبغي أن تراجم العربية أية لغة أخرى

This method aims to directly teach the desired language to the student. So no intermediate language: or mother tongue is adopted at all in its desired language learning path. (طعيمة، ١٩٨٩)

Dr. Al-Khuli said:

بموجب هذه الطريقة، فإن اللغة الأم لا مكان لها في تعليم اللغة الأجنبية

Another mandatory feature of this method is that mother tongue has no place in foreign language education. (الخولي، ١٩٨٦) Dr. Al-Fawzan said:

تتجنب الترجمة، وترى أن استعمال لغة وسيطة في التعليم أمر شديد الخطورة

This method avoids translation. And think that using intermediate language in foreign language learning is very harmful (الفوزان، ٢٠١١). Dr. Rushdie says:

ينبغي تعليم اللغة العربية خلال العربية ذاتها دون أية لغة وسيطة

Arabic should be taught through Arabic itself without any intermediate language. That is why it is called without means or resort-free method. (طعيمة، ١٩٨٩)

Grammar rules are not given much importance in this method. Rather, the emphasis is on the use of language .Dr. Al-Khuli and Dr. Fawzan says:

لا تستخدم هذه الطريقة الأحكام النحوية، لأن مؤيدي هذه الطريقة يرون أن هذه الأحكام لا تعيد في إكتساب المهارة اللغوية المطلوبة

This method does not use grammar rules. Because its supporters think that all these rules of grammar are of no use in acquiring any desired language skills. However, grammar is indirectly mastered by the student through language practice. (الفوزان، ٢٠١١)

Dr. Rushdie says:

النحو وسيلة لتنظيم التعبير اللغوي وضبطه، ومن ثم يتم تعليم النحو العربي بأسلوب غير مباشر من خلال التعبيرات والجمل التي يرد ذكرها في الحوار .

"Grammar is the tool to systematically express and master the language. For this reason, the teaching of Arabic grammar is done in an indirect way through multidimensional language expression and sentences used in conversation.(طعيمة, ١٩٨٩)

C. Reading Method of Arabic Language Teaching

Process of Reading Method:

Practice reading written books starting with phonetic pronunciation:

In this method, the student learns to pronounce the sounds of the desired language and then learns to pronounce by listening to the sentences. Finally learn to read written books .Dr. Rushdie says:

تبدأ هذه الطريقة عادة بفترة يتدرب الطلاب فيها على بعض المهارات الصوتية، فيستمعون لبعض الجمل البسيطة، وينطقون ببعض الأصوات والجمل، حتى بالفون النظام الصوتي، انطلاقاً من مبتدأ مؤداه، أن الصورة التي يكونها المرة عن النظام الصوتي للغة سوف تسهم في تنمية مهاراته في الاتصال برموزها على الصفحة المطبوعة

This approach flourishes in an environment where the essence of learning a foreign language is to have the student read textbooks printed in that language from the outset; No translation will be attempted. And the student's task is to understand its meaning through reading.(طعيمة, ١٩٨٩)

The life of this method is the reading of books on a wide and wide scale. So the bottom line is that the language along with vocabulary and grammar will be mastered by reading.

While reading books written in this method, emphasis is placed on the correct pronunciation of the language. Because written books are usually purer than spoken language. The correct form of the language is known through reading correctly. Dr. Hammadah said:

وبذلك نجد أي من حسنات هذه المدرسة اهتمامها بالنطق السليم واستعمال الوسائل المعينة للتدريب عليه

The good thing about this method is that it is essential to practice and pronounce correctly. (إبراهيم, n.d.)

Emphasizes the use of material:

In this method, the passages presented for the purpose of reading include words that are used in everyday life and are very common. As a result, the language is taught in a progressive way.

Dr. Hammadah said:

واختيار المفردات الشائعة والتدرج في تقديمها ومراعاة ذلك في النصوص المطبوعة

Common vocabulary is chosen in the passages presented for reading, and attention is paid to progression in presentation. And all this is observed in printed textbooks. (إبراهيم, n.d.)

D. The audiolingual method of Arabic Language Teaching

This method is required for the purpose of many language learning methods in a short time and simultaneously practically. In the first chapter it was mentioned that this method made it possible to teach many foreign languages in a very short time to the large American army.

Dr. Hammadah Ibrahim says:

كان هدف المشروع هو أن يمكن الدارس من التحدث بغلة واحدة أو عدة لغات معرفة البلد الذي يستعمل اللغة والتعرف إلى أهله

The purpose of the American language teaching program was to enable the student to converse in one or more languages and to know about the country and its people. (إبراهيم, n.d.)

It can be seen in reality, in a novel method, it was possible to teach 17 languages of different countries to a large number of American troops in just six to nine months.

The ultimate goal of learning a language is to establish direct communication orally, not through grammar, translation, reading or writing. So this method tries to establish direct communication. Dr. Rushdie says:

تنطلق هذه الطريقة من تصور للغة مؤداه أنها مجموعة من الرموز الصوتية التي يتعارف أفراد المجتمع على دلالتها بقصد تحقيق الاتصال بين بعضهم البعض، من هنا فإن الهدف الأساسي في تعليم العربية هو تمكين غير الناطقين بالعربية من الاتصال الفعال بالناطقين بها، بما يتطلبه هذا الاتصال من مهارات مختلفة وبما يدور حوله من مواقف

In the audio-lingual approach, language is thought of as a number of symbolic words; With the help of which people of society establish relationship or communication with each other. Therefore, the purpose of Arabic education for non-Arabs is to enable them to communicate with Arabs in Arabic.(طعيمة, ١٩٨٩)

According to the audiolingual approach, language is not just the written form or skeleton of art or literature; Rather, language is the medium or tool of expression of the style of life and human civilization. So that style can be learned through direct conversation. Dr. Rushdie also says:

إنها ليست مجرد أشكال الفن أو الأدب، أنها أسلوب الحياة التي يعيشها قوم معينون يتكلموه لغة معينة ومن ثم يصبح تدريس الأنماط الثقافية العربية أمرا لازما من خلال تدريب اللغة ذاتها. إنه من الممكن، كما ترى هذه الطريقة، تقديم الأنماط الثقافية من خلال الحوار الذي يقدم في كل درس، إن من الطبيعي أن يدور الحوار حول مواقف الحياة العادية التي يعيشها الناس، مثل تناول الطعام، وأسلوب التحية، والسفر، والزواج وغيرها من أنماط ثقافية مختلفة. وكذلك في مواد القراءة الموسعة، حيث يقدم للدارس نصوص وموضوعات حول مواقف ثقافية معينة

E. Communicative method of Arabic Language Teaching

The method that is invented in the modern era is called 'Communicative Method' in the progress of foreign language teaching methods.

Communication is the method that leads to the acquisition of the four basic skills of language, ie listening, speaking, reading and writing, for the purpose of establishing mutual multidimensional communication. So this method is nothing but a practical activity to acquire the above four skills.

Jill Kerper Mora mentions: Communicative competence is the progressive acquisition of the ability to use a language to achieve one's communicative purpose.(Mora, n.d.)

Communicative competence is the progressive acquisition of the ability to enable people to use a language for communicative purposes.

Dr. Fawzan introduces this method:

هدف هذه الطريقة النهائي اكتساب الدارس القدرة على استخدام اللغة الأجنبية وسيلة اتصال، لتحقيق أغراضه المختلفة، ولا تنتظر هذه الطريقة إلى اللغة على أنها مجموعة من التراكيب والقوالب، مقصودة لذاتها، وإنما تعدها وسيلة للتعبير عن الوظائف اللغوية المختلفة، كالطلب والترجي والأمر والنهي والوصف والتقرير - الخ

The ultimate objective of this method is to enable the student to use the foreign language as a means of communication. This approach does not consider language to be only a number of connected sentences, a structure of sentence formation or an object in itself (the purpose of

knowing language itself). Rather, this approach assumes that language is a means (wasila) of expressing the various purposes associated with language. Such as seek, desire, command, prohibit, describe, report, etc. (الفوزان, ٢٠١١).

Above all in this method a learner is able to establish all kinds of communication between each other in the desired language. Dr. Fawzan says:

الاتصال هو الهدف، وهو الوظيفة الأساس للغة

Communication is the goal and communication is the main function of language. (الفوزان, ٢٠١١).

F. The Eclectic Method of Arabic Language Teaching

In a word, the positive aspects of all the aforementioned methods are characteristic of this method. Since it is created and implemented by combining and combining positive aspects from all methods.

Although the eclectic method is a combination of all the positives of all the previous methods, it is not completely error-free or 100% positive. Because 'summary of all positives of all methods' is not easy. Moreover, when everything is positive, there is negativity hidden behind that positivity. So we have evaluated it by looking at the positive and negative aspects of this method.

As it is an independent and barrier-free method, its positive aspects are high.

Each approach has pros and cons. This method only brings together the good aspects.

Dr. Muhammad Ali al-Khuli said:

كل طريقة في التدريس لها محاسنها، ويمكن الاستفادة منها في تدريس اللغ الأجنبية

Each method has some advantages in teaching. It is possible to achieve the desired results by using those good aspects in foreign language teaching. (الخولي, ١٩٨٦).

As there is no single ideal or model approach, this approach attempts a middle ground.

Dr. Muhammad Ali Al-Khuli said:

التوجد طريقة مثالية تماماً أو خاطئة تماماً، ولكل طريقة مزايا وعيوب، وحجج لها

No single method can be found which is completely followable or every method has its positive features and faults. As there is evidence for it, there are arguments against it. (الخولي, ١٩٨٦).

Since this method has no shape, form or space-occupying character of its own, it can be applied in any country, in any place, in any language, for whatever purpose it is being taught. Thus, this method is able to be selective or universal. Nizar Hussein Wali Says:

It should be pointed out that making use of the positive aspects of different approaches helps the teacher to achieve his aim with his pupils in different learning situations when presenting his materials.(Wali, 2009) Dr. Muhammad Ali Al-Khuli said:

لا توجد طريقة تدريس واحدة تناسب جميع الأهداف وجميع الطلاب وجميع المعلمين وجميع أنواع برامج تدريس اللغات الأجنبية

No single approach can be found that will suit all purposes, all students, all teachers, and all foreign language teaching curricula.(الخولي, ١٩٨٦)

05. Some courses throughout the world specially on Quranic language teaching

According to our analysis, there are three types of methods in the world for teaching Quranic Language. these are:

1. Direct Methods;
2. Grammar- translation Methods;
3. Eclectic Methods.

Details are mentioned below:

1. Direct Methods:

Dr. Abdul Aziz Abdur Rahim Discovered in 1998 by Understand Quran Academy from Hyderabad, India. So far, this method has been translated into 20 international languages, India, Bangladesh, and 25 countries around the world.(Mohsin, 2022) According this approach, there are many courses have developed and conducted in Bangladesh.

Salient features of this method:

1. Attempts are made to understand the Qur'an directly with the words and sentences of the Qur'an;
2. There is no practice in basic practical language;
3. Essential grammar is mentioned;
4. Focus is on reading skills.

Basic problems with this method:

1. Lack of basic and practical language practice makes language learning unsustainable; As a result, even if some simple ta'birat (تعبيرات) of the Qur'an is remembered temporarily, it is not permanent;

2. The complex ta'birat (تعبيرات) of the Qur'an are incomprehensible;
3. All the beauty of Quran cannot be enjoyed.

These courses are mentioned below:

SL	Course name	writer/compiler	Medium Language
1	Quran Explorer	Engineer Naeem Ahmed	Bangla
2	Anibu Quran	Prof. Dr. Matiar Rahman	Bangla
3	Qurani Arabic (Learn the Quran in the language of the Quran)	Sheikh Mahfuz	Bangla
4	The language of Al-Quran, Quranic words (80 percent)	SM Nahid Hasan	Bangla
5	Language of Quran	SM Nahid Hasan	Bangla
6	Commentary on Al-Qur'an: Muhammad	Khalliur Rahman Mumin	Bangla
7	Mukammal Lugatul Quran	Ahmad Karim siddik	Bangla
8	Arabic For Quran (safirul Quran)	Dr. Abul kalam azad	Bangla
9	Read the Quran and understand it.	Emdadul Haque Chowdhury	Bangla
10	Teaching the language of the Holy Quran	Professor Muhammad Hamidur Rahman	Bangla
11	First lesson on understanding the Quran	Abdus Shaheed Nasim	Bangla
12	Understanding the Quraan (An easy Explanation of Arabic Grammar with the Words & Verses of Qur'aan)	Mohammad ibn Saoud Arabic Language Institute	English
13	Learn Arabic Language of Quran	Maktaba dar us salam, riyadh, saudi arabia	English
14	Essentials of Quranic Arabic	masood ahmed rainginwala	English
15	Learn the Language of the Holy Quran	Dr. Abdullah Abbas Nadwi	English
16	Learning Arabic Language the Qur'an	IZZATH UROOSA	English
17	Learn the language of the quran	IQRA International Foundation	English
18	Understanding Al-Quran	http://corpus.quran.com	English
19	Quranic language made easy	Hafiza iffath hasan	English
20	<i>The miraculous language of the Qur'an</i>	Bassam saeh	English
21	Exploring the Level of Understanding the Content of Quran among Diverse Groups of People	Saadah Abd Rahman	English

22	Al Quran the linguistic miracle	Linguisticmiracle.com	English
23	The Teacher's Guide to Quranic Linguistics Levels 1A & 1B	Fahim Qazi	English
24	Quranic Arabic Program	Muhammad Mubashir Nazir	English
25	Towards Understanding Quranic Arabic	Dr Muhammad Ibrahim H. I. Surty	English
26	Quranic Understanding among Non-Native Speaker of Arabic: Malaysian Experts' Perspectives	Hazleena Baharun Saadah Abd Rahman Hishomudin Ahmad Noor Saazai Mat Saad Ikmal Hafiz Jamal	English
27	Literary Miracle of the Quran	Dr. Meraj Ahmad Meraj	English
28	Understanding The Quran Themes and Style	Muhammad Abdel Haleem	English
29	Exploring the quran context and impact	Muhammad Abdel Haleem	English
30	Learning Quranic Arabic for Complete Beginners	Imran Hawramani	English
31	Master Quranic Arabic in 24 hours	<u>Suhaib Sirajudin</u>	English
32	UNDERSTAND QUR'AN For Elementary School Children (Book-1)	Compiled by Dr. Abdulazeez Abdur raheem	English

2. Grammar- translation Methods;

This method is the ancient method of understanding the Quran. However, it is one of the popular methods for understanding the Qur'an even today.

The salient features of this method are:

1. The entire course is arranged in light of the Arabic grammar continuum;
2. Grammar rules are practiced as well as words, phrases and sentences from the Qur'an;
3. There is practical language practice but it is not enough.

Problems of this method:

1. Grammatical approach without emphasis on practical language does not capture language properly;
2. The main purpose of language learning is disrupted;
3. At the end of the day, the Qur'an cannot be understood consistently.

In the light of this method, the following courses have been developed which are famous in the world including Bangladesh; It is mentioned below-

SL	Course name	writer/compiler	Medium Language
1	Lisanul Quran	Teachers of Madrasha ayesha	Urdu & Bangla
2	Essentials of Arabic Grammar for learning Quranic Language	Brig(R) Zahoor Ahmed	Bangla
3	The Qurans Language A New Approach	Noman Ali khan	English
4	Quranic Arabic Grammar	Dr. Matiar Rahman	Bangla
5	Translation page and 6 forms of verb	Dr. Abdul Aziz Abdur Rahim	Bangla
6	Basic Quranic Arabic Grammar	Jamal un Nisa bint rafai	English
7	Morphological Annotation of Quranic Arabic	Kais Dukes and Nizar Habash	English
8	Modern Arabic Grammar	sheikh siraj uddin	Bangla
9	Modern Arabic Grammar	Shahidul Millat	Bangla
10	النحو التطبيقي من القرآن والسنة المستوى الأول	Abdullah A Rahman	Arabic
11	نحو القرآن	Ahmad Abdus Stattar	Arabic

3. Eclectic Method:

In the light of our observation and analysis, this method is the most effective worldwide in teaching the Quranic language. Salient features of this method:

1. The Qur'an is understood in the light of language teaching methods;
2. At the end of the course, practical Arabic language is also understood;
3. Learning the Quranic language is also sustainable due to the acquisition of full proficiency in practical Arabic language.

Limitations of this method:

1. The course takes a long time to complete;
2. Quran cannot be understood without completing the course; In other ways, the ability to understand the Qur'an is created from the beginning.
3. The size of course materials is vast.

Popular Courses of this Method throughout the world:

SL	Course name	writer/compiler	Medium Language
1	الطريق إلى العربية	Abu Taher Misbah	Bangla
2	Arabic Language Learning	Osiur Raman	Bangla
3	درس العربية	Nazmul Hasan	Bangla
4	بداية العربية	S M Nahid Hasan	Bangla
5	الطريق الى العربية	Team Work	Arabic

6	العربية للحياة	Team Work	Arabic
7	العربية للعالم	Hasan Ibn Muhammad	Arabic
9	العربية للناشئين	Mahmud Ismayel	Arabic
10	دروس اللغة العربية لغير الناطقين	V Abdur Rahim	Arabic
11	سلسلة تعليم اللغة العربية جامعة السودان المفتوحة	Team Work	Arabic
12	سلسلة كنوز	Hidaya Ibrahim	Arabic
13	علمي العربية	Murshida Muhammad Rajuk	Arabic
14	العربية تجمعنا	Team Work	Arabic
15	أحب اللغة العربية	Habib Affas	Arabic
16	الكتاب الأساسي	Abdullah Solinam Ar Jarbu	Arabic
17	العربية بين يدي أولادنا	Abdur Rahman Faujan	Arabic
١8	العربية بين يديك	Abdur Rahman Faujan	Arabic
19	القراءة الميسرة	Mahmud Ismayel	Arabic
20	سلسلة جامعة الإمام محمد بن سعود الإسلامية	Team Work	Arabic
٢1	الكتاب في تعلم العربية	Abbas Al Tunusi	Arabic

06. Findings of this study:

There are thousands of Arabic language teaching courses and methods around the world. Arabic language is at the top of the list of languages learned by all peoples of the world, regardless of Muslims and non-Muslims. Different communities are learning this language for different purposes. Religious reasons are one of them. Since the main books of Islam are in Arabic language, to know and understand Islam in detail and fully, Muslims and non-Muslims are interested in learning Arabic language. Based on these needs and demands, the need for teaching Arabic language has arisen all over the world. And in the light of the characteristics of different countries and ethnic groups, different Arabic language teaching courses are designed. But in the light of the recognized methods and natural continuity of language teaching worldwide, there are some language teaching methods that have gained wide acceptance worldwide.

The purpose of teaching the language of the Holy Quran is the methods or courses that are popular worldwide including Bangladesh; from that the analysis of 5 methods or courses with distinct characteristics is mentioned below.

1. الطريق إلى العربية

Author: Abu Taher Misbah

Target Audience: For all students who can read Quran or any Arabic text with Tashkil.

Course Features:

1. At the end of the course, ability to read and understand the Holy Quran, Hadith and other basic and classic books related to Islam; Ability to write Arabic fluently and speak Arabic fluently.
2. The course is designed in light of the natural tendencies of human language learning. Also the continuation of the course is logical in the light of linguistics.
3. Well-planned lessons of one year duration
4. It is possible to get the full result of the course by combining the teaching of the teacher and the mutual group study and individual practice of the students.
5. Course size, number of lessons, volume of each lesson, number of new words per lesson, new sentence structure per lesson, repetition of words and sentence structure of previous lesson in ongoing lesson, all aspects of language teaching method are standard and reasonable.
6. Practices include basic language practice as well as practice in the corresponding texts of the Qur'an and Hadith.
7. No medium language is used.
8. Tashkil of new words and Bengali meanings have been used.
9. Tashkil are used as needed in lectures and exercises. Tashkil is not used in the words that used Tashkil earlier.
10. Cultural issues are systematically highlighted.
11. lessons are arranged through general text.

Course Limitations:

1. Except for the first two lessons, no pictures were used in the content of the course. As a result, the language teaching system has become flawed and complicated.
2. There is no lesson title and no index according to lesson title.
2. There is no specific lesson plan for listening and speaking skills.
3. There is no planned discussion of phonics in the lesson plan.
4. In Lesson Plans, there is no discussion of grammar; As a result, the student is totally dependent on the teaching of the teacher.
5. There are no rich instructions on how to read and practice each lesson; A student has to complete the lessons and exercises as per the instructions of the teacher.

6. Although the course was designed to acquire the ability to read and understand the Qur'an and write in the language of the Qur'an, the words, phrases and sentences of the Qur'an were not adequately and appropriately used in each lesson.

2. دروس اللغة العربية

Author: Dr. V. Abdur Rahim

Target Audience: For all students who can read Quran or any Arabic text with Tashkil.

Course Features:

1. At the end of the course, reading, writing, listening and speaking skills will be developed as well as understanding the Holy Quran, Hadith and other classic Arabic texts.
2. Each lesson is decorated with dialogue; By doing this, the speaking skills of the students will be developed.
3. There are adequate and planned exercises at the end of each lesson; Through which reading, writing and speaking skills increase.
4. The first few lessons used pictures.
5. Cultural aspects are systematically maintained in the lessons.
6. Well-planned lessons of one year duration
7. Course size, number of lessons, volume of each lesson, number of new words per lesson, new sentence structure per lesson, repetition of words and sentence structure of previous lesson in ongoing lesson, all aspects of language teaching method are standard and reasonable.
8. Practices include basic language practice as well as practice in the corresponding texts of the Qur'an and Hadith.
9. The book is divided into 3 parts. Out of which the first two parts deal only with continuous language reading and practice and the third part deals with language practice as well as basic grammar.

Limitations of This Course

1. Except for the first two lessons, no pictures were used in the content of the course. As a result, the language teaching system has become flawed and complicated.
2. There is no lesson title and no index according to lesson title.
2. There is no specific lesson plan for listening and speaking skills.
4. There are no rich instructions on how to read and practice each lesson; A student has to complete the lessons and exercises as per the instructions of the teacher.
5. Although the course was designed to acquire the ability to read and understand the Qur'an and write in the language of the Qur'an, the words, phrases and sentences of the Qur'an were not adequately and appropriately used in each lesson.

3. The Quran's Language: A New Approach

Writer: Noman Ali Khan

Target Audience: For all students who can read Quran or any Arabic text with Tashkil.

Features of This Course:

1. The course materials are divided into two parts. One. Main lesson; Two. exercise or work book
2. The course is designed grammatically.
3. In sense of topic, the course is basically divided into 3 parts. A. Nahu (Phraseology); B. Sorf (verbal Vocabulary) C. Rhetoric
4. The course is structured using the words, phrases and sentences of the Qur'an with reference to grammatical consistency and principles.
5. The course is designed to focus basically on reading skills.
6. At the end of the course, the ability to understand and realize the Quran will be developed.
7. The inclusion of rhetoric makes this course different from other courses.

Course Limitations:

1. Apart from reading skills, there are no appropriate lessons for the other 3 language skills.
2. Lacking the basic sequence of language teaching for grammatical continuum; As a result, language learning becomes unintelligible.
3. Medium language is used throughout the course; As a result, the principle of language teaching is broken.
4. The whole course is arranged only with grammar and words, phrases and sentences of the Qur'an, there is no practice in basic language; This process has been tough and hard for learners.
5. No images were used; As a result, it is very difficult to master new words.
6. There is no opportunity to practice I'rab due to only being equipped with grammar and the Qur'an.

4. Lisanul Quran (لسان القرآن)

Writer: Teachers of Madrasah Ayeasha, Pakistan

Target Audience: For all students who can read Quran or any Arabic text with Tashkil.

Features of This Course:

1. This course is divided into 3 parts. 'Nahu' (النحو) is discussed in the first and last part and 'Saraf' (الصرف) is discussed in the second part.
2. The course is structured in the light of ancient grammar translation methods. But adequate practice of language learning is also given along with the grammar translation method.
3. All essential chapters of Arabic grammar are included.

4. Beside grammar there is enough language practice.
5. Each grammar rule is accompanied by ample examples.
6. At the end of the course, learners will be able to translate any basic Arabic text including Quran, Hadith.
7. Cultural approach has been highlighted.

Limitations of this Course:

1. Apart from reading skills, there are no appropriate lessons for the other 3 language skills.
2. Lacking the basic sequence of language teaching for grammatical continuum; As a result, language learning becomes unintelligible.
3. Medium language is used throughout the course; As a result, the principle of language teaching is broken.
5. No images were used; As a result, it is very difficult to master new words.
6. There is no opportunity to practice I'rab due to only being equipped with grammar and the Qur'an.
7. The method of teaching new words is not methodical.
8. There is no proper practice with the words, phrases and sentences of the Qur'an; Because of which the main purpose is defeated.
9. There is no planned time frame for every lesson.

5. تعليم العربية للناطقين بغيرها (الكتاب الأساسي).

Writer: Teachers of University of Ummul Qura

Target Audience: For all students who can read Quran or any Arabic text with Tashkil.

Features of This Course:

1. The course is designed with almost the overall characteristics of a language course. For example: the four language skills, culture and the three elements of language are almost always included Methodically;
2. The entire course is divided into 6 books;
3. From basic to advanced level;
4. At the end of the course, learners will be able to read, listen, understand, speak and write any Arabic text including to read Quran and Hadith;
5. The course lessons are structured with dialogues and Text;
6. pictures are used in teaching new words;
7. A discussion of grammar has been added from the second volume;

8. The use of Tashkil in words, Phrases and Sentences is Methodical.

Course Limitations:

1. The size of the course is very large; As a result, any new learner will lose interest;
2. In the first Part, pictures have been used of new words but no pictures from the second part;
3. There are all kinds of exercises to understand the Qur'an, but in many cases there are many exercises that are unnecessary; Which applies to full Arabic language courses.

07. Our Recommendations for developing a Arabic Language Course that may be the most perfect course on understanding Quran:

After a thorough analysis of the features and limitations of the above courses, if a course can be designed in the light of the following recommendations, students of the Quranic language will be benefited more in terms of learning. Following are the recommendations:

1. designing courses in the light of rich and acceptable methods of language teaching;
2. Language teaching should include four skills, culture and three elements, but among the four skills, speaking skills are not as important in Quranic language;
3. Use appropriate images for each new word, dialogue and text;
4. Course size cannot be increased; So that students do not lose interest;
5. Beginning with basic and practical language exercises;
6. Along with practical language practice, there will be provision of direct practice by words, phrases and sentences of the Qur'an according to necessity;
7. Gradually the basic rules of grammar should be added to Basic language;
8. Full and clear instructions will be given to the students in the course; So that the students do not have to be 100% dependent on the instructors;
9. Exercise cannot be overdone; A moderate number of exercises should be added;
10. Lessons will consist of both conversational and textual lessons;
11. A lesson will include as many lessons as possible in a class;
12. New words, phrases and sentences will be fully formed;
13. Each lesson will have special exercises on phonics;
14. The course will be continuous from the very beginning i.e. the alphabet to the end i.e. students who have not yet learned the Arabic alphabet can also start this course.

08. Conclusion:

In order to present the language of the Qur'an in an easy-to-understand way to the Bengali-speaking population, numerous courses running worldwide have been analysed in detail. After selecting the most popular, appropriate and methodical courses from

numerous courses, the positive and negative aspects of these courses have been carefully analysed. Keeping that analysis in mind, some important recommendations are given to follow the state-of-the-art method of language teaching. We hope that if a course is designed in the light of the above recommendations, the Bengali speaking population will be able to master the language of the Quran more easily.

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